

Public Search Interest in E-Cigarettes Versus Cigarettes in Canada

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Preferred Presentation Type: ePoster presentation

Topic: Digital Surveillance of Tobacco Interest

Title: Public Search Interest in E-Cigarettes Versus Cigarettes in Canada

Objectives: To examine Google Search trends in e-cigarettes (vaping) versus cigarettes among Canadians over a five-year period (2020-2025) in order to determine public interest in different forms of smoking.

Background: Interest in e-cigarettes among Canadians, especially youth, has risen rapidly in contrast to traditional cigarette use. Recent research suggests that adolescents who use e-cigarettes are more likely to transition to conventional cigarette smoking in adulthood, and online tobacco advertising plays a vital role in this progression. However, little is known about current online search activity concerning e-cigarettes versus traditional cigarettes in Canada. Therefore, examining the search trends of Canadians regarding different smoking methods would further inform targeted interventions, preventative research, and tobacco advertising policy.

Methods: For trend analysis, I utilized Google Trends and compared the topics “Electronic Cigarette” and “Cigarette.” I set the location to Canada and the time range from June 2020 to June 2025, while applying the filters “All Categories” (displayed all relevant search terms across all categories) and “Web Search” (search results were exclusively from the Google Search engine). Subsequently, the generated data included an “Interest Over Time” graph and a data table comparing the weekly number of searches for each topic.

Results: The Google Trends data displayed a total of 19,293 searches for “Electronic Cigarette” and 8,253 for “Cigarette”. The average relative weekly search interest for “Electronic Cigarette” ($M = 73.6$, $SD = 11.4$) was higher than it was for “Cigarette” ($M = 31.5$, $SD = 3.3$). A paired t-test confirmed this difference as statistically significant, $t(261) = 73.66$, $p < 0.001$.

Conclusions: Higher relative search interest for “Electronic Cigarette” compared to “Cigarette” may reflect changing tobacco use patterns, most likely among Canadian youth. In light of this trend, researchers and policymakers should consider distributing youth-focused surveys on smoking behaviours to 16 to 21-year-olds and public health campaigns focusing specifically on e-cigarettes, given their increasing popularity.

Keyword 1: E-Cigarettes

Keyword 2: Google Trends

Keyword 3: Smoking Trends

Keyword 4: Online Health Behaviour

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